

A Preliminary Record of Butterfly Diversity within a locality of Thiruvananthapuram Corporation limit

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Lime Swallowtail

Butterflies are insects beloved by all and as a group have been extensively studied. This short work was aimed at exploring the existing diversity of butterflies in a waterlogged area located at the heart of the city. The site was of an extent of 60-70 cents in the middle of Thampanoor City (8.492N 76.949E) with a variety of shrub species and a few tree types (Figure 1). Among the notable flora were *Passiflora* spp., *Calotropis* spp., *Moringa oleifera*, etc.

The study was carried out in September 2021 and all were observations made between 09:00h and 12:00h, the peak hours of butterfly activity. Visual Encounter Survey (VES) was the method followed. A Nikon D5600 DSLR camera with a 70–300mm lens was used for photo documentation. Species identification was confirmed using field guides (Kunte 2000; Kehimkar 2008; Kunte, Sondhi & Roy 2018) and consultation with experts.

20 species of butterflies belonging to 5 families were recorded (Table 1). Nymphalidae was the most speciose family with 9 species due to the presence of some common and widespread species such as Tawny Coster and Plain Tiger. It was followed by Lycaenidae (6 species), Hesperiiidae (3 species), Pieridae (1 species) and Papilionidae (1 species) (Figure 2). The relative abundance of the families along with the most abundant species in it is given in Table 2.

The Tawny Coster was the most prevalent species, perhaps from the plentiful availability of its hostplant, *Passiflora* spp., at the site. Gram Blue was the only protected species among those recorded, classified

Figure 1. Study Site

in the Schedule II of the Indian Wildlife Protection Act (WPA) of 1972. The lack of nectar plant diversity along with only a few species of larval hostplants could perhaps explain the small number of butterfly species recorded.

A more detailed and year-round study is needed for a full insight on the butterfly

Figure 2. The family-wise distribution of butterflies at the study site

Family	Relative Abundance	Most Abundant Species
Nymphalidae	45%	Tawny Coster
Lycaenidae	30%	Tiny Grass Blue
Hesperiiidae	15%	Chestnut Bob
Pieridae	5%	Psyche
Papilionidae	5%	Lime Swallowtail

diversity at the location. The above point is significant in today's scenario where developmental activities are causing rapid deterioration and destruction of urban green spaces and the biodiversity therein. Local biodiversity documentation and monitoring are key to the creation of baseline data on urban biodiversity and understanding the changes that occur over time.

Table 1. Checklist of the recorded butterflies from the study location

Sl.No.	
	Family Papilionidae
1	Lime Swallowtail <i>Papilio demoleus</i>
	Family Nymphalidae
2	Plain Tiger <i>Danaus chrysippus</i>
3	Striped Tiger <i>Danaus genutia</i>
4	Tawny Coster <i>Acraea terpsicore</i>
5	Lemon Pansy <i>Junonia lemonias</i>
6	Common Castor <i>Ariadne merione</i>
7	White Four-ring <i>Ypthima ceylonica</i>
8	Common Five-ring <i>Ypthima baldus</i>
9	Common Evening Brown <i>Melanitis leda</i>
10	Common Sailor <i>Neptis hylas</i>
	Family Pieridae
11	Psyche <i>Leptosia nina</i>
	Family Lycaenidae
12	Plains Cupid <i>Luthrodes pandava</i>
13	Western Centaur Oakblue <i>Arhopala centaurus</i>
14	Dark Grass Blue <i>Zizeeria karsandra</i>
15	Lesser Grass Blue <i>Zizina otis</i>
16	Tiny Grass Blue <i>Zizula hylax</i>
17	Gram Blue <i>Euchrysops cnejus</i>
	Family Hesperidae
18	Chestnut Bob <i>Iambrix salsala</i>
19	Indian Palm Bob <i>Suastus gremius</i>
20	Conjoined Swift <i>Pelopidas conjuncta</i>

References

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- Kunte, K., 2000. *Butterflies of Peninsular India*. Hyderabad: Universities Press and Bengaluru: Indian Academy of Sciences.
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Lemon Pansy

Tiny Grass Blue